

Mobile Communications with Intermittent and Renewable Energy

Omer H. Abdelrahman, *Member, IEEE* and Erol Gelenbe, *Fellow, IEEE*,

Abstract—Mobile communications are a powerful contributor to social and economic development worldwide, and in particular in less developed parts of the world. However the extension and penetration of mobile communications are often hampered by the state of the electrical grid, which may not cover all areas and which may also be intermittent and unreliable. Thus we review some of the economic and technological challenges for mobile telecommunications that integrate and exploit potentially plentiful renewable energy sources, such as photovoltaic, in developing areas of the world. Such sources of energy for communication networks are also useful to mitigate the environmental impact of energy consumption of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) world-wide. However renewable energy sources are themselves intermittent, and this raises new challenges concerning network design. Hence this paper also develops an analytical approach that can be used to evaluate the quality of service of networks that operate with intermittent sources of energy.

Keywords- Off-grid Communications; Rural Development; Intermittent Energy; Energy Harvesting; Quality of Service

I. INTRODUCTION

Electrical energy is needed to manufacture, operate and cool ICT equipment. Indeed, the electrical energy consumption just needed to operate ICT systems is growing worldwide, and had exceeded 900 TWH per year in 2012, or more than the energy consumption of Japan [1]. While in developed parts of the world ICT systems are designed with the expectation that a steady and reliable source of stable electricity is available everywhere, this is not the case in many areas of the developing world.

Within ICT, mobile telephony plays a key role in development [2] including health provisioning, education, safety and security, the search for opportunities for remunerated work, information regarding funds transfer from abroad, on top of the need to communicate with remote villages and family members. Another important aspect is the geographic mobility of the users themselves, due to seasonal effects, nomadic behaviors due to their livelihood or to changing security conditions.

In Africa as a whole, and specifically in many areas of sub-Saharan Africa, access to mobile telephony is paradoxically ahead of the access to stable sources of electrical energy, as stated by the Brookings Institution indicated in 2015 that the fraction of the population in Africa that has access to mobile telephony (39%) exceeds the population having access to electricity (32%), emphasizing the importance of mobile

communications for economic development [3]. Indeed, according to Forbes [4] (Oct. 19, 2015) “two out of every three people in sub-Saharan Africa live without electricity, according to the US government’s Power Africa statistics”, but “that number is going to drop as renewable energy – in particular solar – becomes more prevalent and accessible on the continent”. In addition, “The African Renewable Energy Initiative plans to develop at least 10 GW of new renewable energy generation capacity by 2020, and at least 300 GW by 2030” (The Guardian, Sep. 7, 2016) [5].

A. Impact of Telecommunication on Development

The relationship between telecommunication development and economic growth has been explored widely in the literature. Overall, research has shown that telecommunication services have a positive effect on all aspects of the economy, including economic growth, productivity and job creation. These positive contributions have been observed in both developed and developing nations, although it is commonly accepted [6] that the higher the penetration of telecommunications the more important is their contribution to economic growth. In other words, the economic benefits may only become significant once penetration levels reach a certain critical mass.

On the other hand, the effect of telecommunication services is not the same in all parts of the world. For example, in developing countries mobile payment has boomed due to the limited payment methods and tools available and majority of people being unbanked. Furthermore by utilizing innovative applications of mobile technology and infrastructure operators can become off-grid energy providers, presenting both a significant growth opportunity for companies and a key input for many rural economic activities [7]. The impact on the overall economy can therefore exceed all expectation provided the services are directed towards the key areas for development.

Also, access to telecommunication services and the Internet is rapidly becoming part of the necessities in life, not only for advanced economies but also in regions where mobile phones had been recently introduced – in one survey in Sudan users expressed their unwillingness to give up their mobiles second to their homes¹.

While mobile telephony is a key enabler of development in developing economies, availability of electricity is often a stumbling block. Remote areas of several countries are unable to receive *stable* mobile communication services because of the lack of stable electricity supplies. As operators venture into

E. Gelenbe and O.H. Abdelrahman are with the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Imperial College, London SW7 2BT, UK, email: {e.gelenbe,o.abd06}@imperial.ac.uk.

¹Throughout the paper we present examples from Sudan compiled by a project collaborator while leading the telecommunication regulatory body of Sudan between 2009 and 2014

more remote locations to achieve universal coverage, due to either government mandates or commercial drivers, the number of off-grid and poor-grid base stations (BSs) is expected to grow globally by 16% between 2014 and 2020 [8], [9]. Thus, viable solutions are needed to reduce the infrastructure cost of establishing dependable wireless communications in such areas, and failure to do so will only result in widening the development gap between developing and industrial countries.

B. Contributions of the Paper

This paper has two objectives. First of all, it summarises the challenges and opportunities associated with deploying dependable wireless communications, with a particular view towards less developed rural areas in Africa or Asia, or remote areas in Europe, Australia and the Americas, where the electricity from the grid may be unreliable or unavailable and renewable energy can be a useful complement. We also outline the main system requirements, and recent developments in mobile networks that enable them to operate with renewable energy at reasonable costs. This review complements recent surveys on the subject as follows:

- We survey the whole technology landscape from the access network and backhaul options, to recharging solutions, to data analytics and micro-grid design tools. Previous reviews [9]–[11] have focused on certain of these technical areas.
- We consider the case where renewable energy is necessary rather than just desirable as in [12].
- We briefly survey research on energy scheduling which is meant to deliver need-based energy parsimoniously so as to attempt to meet the required system quality of service with the least possible energy consumption.
- However we do not survey different power supply technologies for off-grid BSs which are covered adequately in other studies [13].

The second objective of the paper is to analyse the performance of a multi-hop backhaul network that operates in packet mode with an intermittent supply of energy. This work, detailed in Sections IV and V, discusses three cases:

- In the first case, we assume that the backhaul network is so fast that no buffering of packet is needed. Furthermore, we assume that the system is so efficiently designed that each node only consumes energy when it is actually processing and forwarding packets, while no energy is consumed when a node is inactive. Packet loss is assumed to occur when a packet attempts to transit through a node that has run out of energy, as when its energy battery is depleted and its energy source (grid or harvesting) is not providing power.
- The second case assumes that nodes store packets until they can be forwarded, and the nodes are kept on even when they have no packets to forward. Contrary to the previous case, they consume the same amount of energy, independently of whether they have packet to forward or not. In addition, we suppose that the system uses memory technologies that preserve the stored packets even when a node is not powered due to lack of energy in its battery or

its external energy sources do not provide power. Thus, in this case packets in the memory of a node are preserved, while those in transit may be lost.

- The third case is similar to the second one, but we assume that nodes that run out of energy will lose all the packets that they store in their memory.

For all of these cases, we only derive expressions for average number of packet retransmissions needed to achieve successful forwarding of a packet, and the packet loss probabilities, on a single multi-hop path in the backhaul network, in the presence of cross traffic at each node, and intermittent power supply at all of the nodes. We expect that this analytical approach will be extended to general network topologies in future work, and will also allow the computation of the resulting network delays.

II. ECONOMIC CHALLENGES AND REQUIREMENTS

This section outlines the main economic barriers facing mobile network operators in areas where access to stable electricity supply is not available. We then discuss the incentives available for operators to reach remote populations in Africa, and the trends that drive the growth of renewable energy over diesel generators (DGs) in those settings. Based on this analysis, we derive a set of requirements that should be addressed by future deployments and research works.

A. Operators' Challenges in Rural Sites

When operators consider extending telecommunication services to an area, the decision is governed by two related factors: i) the economic feasibility of the area which depends on the size of population, purchasing power, etc., and ii) the availability of basic infrastructures such as electricity and backhauling connection. The challenges facing the deployment of cellular services in rural and remote sites are related to these two factors as elaborated in the following.

1) *Lack of a clear business case:* In contrast to urban environments, rural areas tend to have smaller populations widely distributed over a large geographic land. Providing coverage for such scattered communities requires deploying many small sites that must also be inter-connected and backhauled to the rest of the network, thus increasing the average cost per mobile user. In addition, lack of demographic data (age, education, gender, etc.) and of accurate information about the culture and lifestyle of those communities make it difficult to estimate in advance the traffic demand and power needs of remote sites. The problem of demand prediction and site dimensioning is exacerbated by the lower, or harder to evaluate, degree of exposure to ICT in rural populations as compared to their urban counterparts: people who are exposed to ICT are likely to use mobile services if provided to them, while people who never or rarely used telecommunications may take more time to adopt and adapt to these new services. Also the introduction of mobile services will inevitably increase the need for power, and so operators often face two difficult business choices: over-dimensioning the system in anticipation of future demands that are hard to predict, or bearing the extra cost of constantly upgrading the system to meet the shifts in population's habits.

2) *High initial and recurring investment*: Rural areas are likely to be far from communications infrastructure, leaving operators with no choice but to lease satellite connections and deploy a very small aperture terminal (VSAT) at each of the remote sites for backhaul connectivity outside the region. VSAT systems however are among the most expensive transmission media, and this is one of the main factors for recurring costs to be particularly high in rural sites. In addition to poor communications infrastructure, the sites may not have access to the electricity grid and rely on independent power supplies such as diesel generators (DGs) which also have high CAPEX and OPEX. Thus, when service providers compare the initial and recurring costs of a remote site, to the estimated income taking into account the average revenue per user (ARPU) and the estimated population, those figures create infeasible return on investment.

B. Incentives for Operators to Extend Connectivity

One of the ITU recommendations that was applied in most of the African countries is the establishment of a Universal Service Fund (USF) similar to the one used in the US since 1997. The USF is intended to assist in covering the CAPEX needed to connect deprived remote areas, and also to share OPEX during the early stages of operation. It is controlled by national telecommunication regulators and is supported by charging telecommunications companies a fee. Typically, for a site to be funded by UCF an initial study should indicate clearly that recovery from losses is possible within a reasonable limited period.

In countries such as the Sudan, USF is highly needed since the electricity grid covers only 40% of the total land area. The fund has proven to be very successful, and companies have been able to recover from losses quite quickly, demonstrating that telecommunication has a strong impact on the habits of people and motivates them to be economically more active. Indeed, in one remote site where an open market had been organised once a week, it was held two or three times a week after telecommunication services were introduced to the area. More economic activities were noted and the standard of living was also improved.

C. Drivers for Renewable Energy Growth in Mobile Networks

Photovoltaic (PV) and other energy harvesters with batteries present a huge potential for the mobile industry in remote areas, provided CAPEX is not prohibitively high (since their OPEX is nearly zero). There are currently a number of trends that drive the move from DGs to greener alternatives for off-grid and poor-grid sites.

First, renewable options are becoming more economically viable as technological advancements reduce the amount of energy needed to power BSs. These developments are discussed in Sec. III-A1.

Second, the prices of solar energy systems have fallen by more than 80% over the last 10 years; the average cost of a solar cell in Jan. 2017 is only about \$0.36 per watt [14]. Similarly, the advent of small wind turbines has made wind energy more affordable, enabling operators to use hybrid

solar-wind systems [15] that provide a more steady supply of energy since the two sources have complimentary profiles [16]. Hybrid renewable-DG solutions can also provide a good compromise between the high CAPEX and low OPEX of renewable energy and the relatively low CAPEX but high OPEX of DGs [13]. On the other hand, energy storage technologies have not experienced the same evolution, but battery costs are expected to fall dramatically in the next decade along with a substantial improvement in performance.

A third driver for the growth of renewable over DGs is the prevalence of energy service companies which handle the power system investment and management for a mobile site in exchange for a fee [17]; such energy outsourcing model enables operators to focus on their core business. Also other forms of this business model are emerging, such as infrastructure sharing and outsourcing, helping to alleviate the high CAPEX of remote sites and facilitate quick network roll-out. In the sharing model, multiple operators share support equipment such as power system, towers, etc. but install separate telecommunication modules, while with infrastructure outsourcing the whole site is owned and operated by a third party which lets it to multiple operators.

D. Requirements for Rural Communications

Following our previous discussion, we proceed to identify the main requirements that enable feasible deployments of mobile networks in the absence of access to stable electricity supply. The requirements cover the radio access network, backhaul connection between the radio and core networks and recharging solution for mobile devices.

1) *Access network*: In contrast to standard BSs whose power consumption (including cooling, etc.) can reach 1-3 kilowatts and are designed to support hundreds to a few thousands users [10], [12], the access network of an off-grid or poor-grid site must consume very low power to be able to operate with limited energy supply and storage, while at the same time covering highly dispersed populations. These two conflicting objectives require distinctly different designs to conventional networks which typically utilise high-power macro BSs for coverage in less densely populated regions. Moreover, the access network may need to be moved regularly following geographic mobility of the users themselves due to nomadic behaviors or to changing security conditions.

2) *Backhaul*: While mobile BSs that support today's public communication infrastructure are typically tethered to wired backbone networks, either through LAN or microwave links, rural sites rely on expensive satellite connections which constitute a major component of a site's total OPEX. Solutions that take into account the needs and the communication patterns of the targeted users, and utilise novel multi-hop networking technologies, can reduce or eliminate these prohibitive costs.

3) *Recharging solutions*: Any off-grid solution must incorporate facilities for end users to recharge their mobile phones, otherwise the offered telecommunication services cannot be consumed and investments will not be recovered within a reasonable time frame.

III. ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES

This section describes existing and emerging technologies that facilitate the transition to renewable energy in remote and rural areas. The analysis focuses on advances in ICT rather than in power supply solutions which have been covered elsewhere, e.g. [13].

A. Access Network

1) *Energy-efficient BSs*: A BS consists of three main network elements: a baseband unit (BBU) which performs the processing of the radio protocols; a radio frequency (RF) part which interconverts digital baseband and analogue signals and provides power amplification/filtering of RF signals for transmission/reception over the air; and a transport unit which handles the transfer of data and control traffic between the BS and the core network. Other auxiliary elements include a cooling system, a power supply unit and a control unit. In traditional BS deployments, power consumption is dominated by [10] the RF unit, where most of the power provided by the amplifier is wasted on the feeder connecting to the antenna, as well as by the cooling system.

Modern BS designs have significantly reduced the amount of renewable capacity required to operate at a remote site where electricity from the grid may not be available or it may be unreliable. In such circumstances, intermittent sources of energy from renewable sources such as photovoltaic and wind can be the main, or the complementary, sources of electricity. These technological advancements include:

- Architectures that separate the RF unit from the digital BBU, placing the former at the remote radio head (RRH) close to or even integrated with the antenna to reduce power loss in the feeder. The RRH is connected to the BBU over a digital interface with fiber using standards such as the ETSI's Open Radio equipment Interface (ORI), the Open Base Station Architecture Initiative (OBSAI) or the Common Public Radio Interface (CPRI).
- Power amplifiers that dynamically adjust their input voltage to match the power needed for the output signal [10], reducing the amount of power wasted as heat due to mismatch between the signal envelope and the voltage supply level.
- High-efficiency rectifiers that minimise losses of AC/DC conversion for radio equipment and battery charging.
- Outdoor BSs that can operate in higher ambient temperatures and without power-hungry air conditioning systems [16], facilitated by the reduced heat emanating from modern electronics, power amplifiers and power rectifiers.
- Energy-aware software and hardware that enable switching off resources [18], [19] or adjusting coverage area (e.g., cell breathing or zooming [20]) in response to changing traffic and energy conditions. Some of these mechanisms can be implemented within the self organizing network (SON) paradigm which has been defined and specified by 3GPP² and is intended to automate

the configuration, optimisation and healing of mobile networks.

- Cloud radio access network (C-RAN): In this novel architecture, the BBUs of several BSs can be integrated into a single component, allowing to optimise the number of active BBUs and signal processing at a multi-cell level for cost and energy efficiency [21]. This design is an evolution of the decoupled architecture described above, where multiple distributed RRHs can share not only a single BBU but a pool of BBUs, thus providing greater flexibility in network planning and deployment. However, C-RAN may not be the future technology-of-choice for rural sites as it requires the existence of a low-latency transport network to connect the RRHs and BBU pool, plus its potential benefits are more pronounced in dense scenarios.

2) *Wireless LAN*: IEEE 802.11 (WiFi) offers a cost-effective alternative to traditional BSs in rural settings: the radio technology is inexpensive, its open source nature enables rapid prototyping and development, and the small size of access points (APs) reduces infrastructure costs. Owing to their operation in unlicensed spectrums, WiFi APs are required to have very low maximum transmit power which depends on local regulations. Where interference is unlikely, such as in remote and rural sites, operators can obtain licenses to deploy higher power APs, allowing them to provide voice over IP (VoIP) and other broadband services.

There are many successful rural WiFi deployments around the world; some of these experiences are reported in [22] for India, and in [23]–[25] for the Scottish Highlands and Islands. Nonprofit organisations such as Green WiFi³ and Inveneo⁴ have completed projects in Kenya, Senegal, Uganda and Haiti to name just a few.

3) *Mobile cell sites*: The network topology may need to change to support populations that move for water, food and work opportunities in large rural areas. Providing continuous coverage in locations with seasonal migrations is not cost effective, requiring the BSs themselves to be mobile for optimal positioning as a function of network traffic, end-user mobility patterns, and reachability to the backbone network. There are different types of mobile cell sites including:

- Cell on wheels: BSs are mounted on vehicles for mobility, offering the added advantage of having an additional (emergency) source of electricity produced via the vehicles' engines.
- Rapid deployment units: These are BSs transportable on trucks with flange or self-mounting pole. RDUs are traditionally used to provide emergency communications during disasters, temporary expansion of the network or capacity enhancement for major events such as trade shows and sporting events.
- Low-altitude platforms: A LAP is an airborne system (e.g. a tethered helium balloon or kite) capable of lifting BS equipment to heights between 300m and 4 km [26]. Similar to RDUs, LAPs are designed for emergency

²<http://www.3gpp.org/technologies/keywords-acronyms/105-son>

³<http://borgenproject.org/green-wifi-provides-wi-fi-to-developing-nations/>

⁴<http://www.inveneo.org/projects/broadband-for-good/>

relief [27] and to supplement existing communication infrastructure [26]. On the other hand, since the height of a LAP is easily adjustable, it is more flexible than a RDU as it can optimise the amount of energy extracted from wind and coverage area without incurring additional costs.

- High-altitude platforms: HAPs have been employed in the US for many years, primarily by government and military, to deliver wireless services in remote locations⁵. Also, significant R&D activities were recently undertaken by large Internet companies such as Google⁶ and Facebook⁷ to develop a global network of HAPs, with the aim of providing Internet access to rural and remote areas worldwide. Such ambitious projects require a global footprint and massive investments – neither may be available to operators – but they have the potential to bridge, for good, the broadband gap in Africa and elsewhere. Meanwhile, mobile vendors and operators will continue to search for other short-term solutions.

B. Backhaul

1) *Mobile edge computing*: MEC [28] is an architecture that incorporates more intelligence into the BS's design so that it can operate as a stand-alone network (see [29] for a solution offered by Nokia). MEC can reduce the costs of backhaul connections, by exploiting the communication patterns of rural communities which are markedly different from their urban counterparts. For example, in many rural areas of the Sudan the majority of communications have been observed to be local, and so it is both wasteful and costly to backhaul all traffic to the core network for routing and billing purposes. In such cases, MEC enables a BS to handle local calls with limited or no interactions with the core network. In effect, the communication path for local traffic is “short-circuited” to bypass expensive satellite links, thus increasing the number of sites that can be supported per link.

2) *Multi-hop networking*: Multi-hop communications offer another alternative that can reduce or eliminate the need for expensive satellite connections while maintaining acceptable quality of service (QoS) in the presence of limited energy supply and storage. The idea is to use a combination of repeaters to extend coverage by amplifying and retransmitting mobile signals, and a multi-hop routing mechanism to enable BSs that are closer to the network infrastructure to act as relays for those that are farther away [22], [24]. In the case of alternative paths in the network, there are also issues about how the traffic should be routed as a function of energy harvesting and of the storage of energy itself in batteries, and how energy-aware routing itself affects resource provisioning in the network [30]. Thus, the design and management of such systems will be more complex, and the multi-hop nature of the network makes it important to evaluate how the performance of the network as a whole (and not just a single node) is affected by renewable energy and possible outages.

⁵<http://www.spacedata.net/>

⁶<https://x.company/loom/>

⁷<https://code.facebook.com/posts/268598690180189>

C. Recharging Solutions

In order to allow off-grid users to recharge their phones, a number of technologies are available:

1) *Solar phones*: Those are low power, low cost devices with a built-in solar panel directly powering them. The phones provide very basic functionality due to their limited power supply.

2) *External chargers*: Here chargers are powered by renewable energy (e.g. solar, wind or kinetic) providing access to electricity for both mobile phones as well as other low power devices. An interesting example of a kinetic charger, developed by Nokia for Kenya, is a bicycle kit which uses a dynamo attached to the bicycle wheel to charge a phone.

3) *Charging at BSs*: In this approach, excess power from a BS is used for charging phones. This approach is most suitable for sites equipped with DGs, as renewable-operated sites have limited excess power. It offers a number of advantages: it does not require a dedicated infrastructure, it can be operated by the person typically hired to maintain the site, and it is naturally located close to the community.

4) *Dedicated charging stations*: This solution typically comprises a solar harvester with battery and USB outlets, and uses either mobile money or airtime credit as means to collect payments for the energy service⁸. A pay-as-you-go (PAYG) model which enables users to consume airtime credit to recharge phones offers the advantage of being familiar to locals, eliminating the need for customer education, and is also more viable in markets with low mobile money penetration. A recent case study by GSMA [31] indicates that PAYG energy service generates the same gross revenue as (and sometimes more than) voice and SMS, while reducing churn for the mobile operator.

D. Data Analytics

Data has always played a major role in the planning of mobile networks, and rural areas are no exception. Information that can be exploited at the initial network setup phase includes the target region's precise terrain topography; human settlements; levels of human concentration and typical mobility, communication patterns and needs; critical infrastructures for health, education and security; and the known annual characteristics of sunlight and wind.

Once the network is operational, call detail records and network measurements may be utilised to further optimise the network deployment, and also as a proxy for planning other critical services like energy provisioning [32].

E. Micro-grid Design Tools

There are several optimisation software tools that can be used for designing renewable energy BSs. The inputs needed usually include: power system options such as DGs, batteries, PV panels, wind turbines and other components; site weather data such as solar insolation, wind speed and temperature which are typically imported or downloaded from online

⁸For an example of a mobile power as a service solution see BuffaloGrid (<http://buffalogrid.com/>)

databases; load profile; and economic factors that may include lifetime, interest rate, CAPEX/OPEX of the various available technologies and payback period. Such software tools will then produce the most cost-effective configurations based on the inputs provided and the constraints imposed by the user such as fraction of load served, proportion of renewable energy, or CO₂ emissions.

The current industry standard in this area is HOMER (<http://www.homerenergy.com>) which was developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory of the US and has been applied extensively in telecommunication (e.g., [15], [33], [34]). It evaluates all configurations over a range of sensitivities, by simulating the system for one year (in steps of 1-60 minutes) which is assumed to be representative of every other year of the project lifetime. The Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory's DER-CAM (<https://building-microgrid.lbl.gov/projects/der-cam>) formulates the model as a mixed integer linear program using IBM CPLEX optimiser, providing both the optimal mix and the operating schedule of energy resources; the former calculation is available free of charge as a web service.

iHOGA (<http://hoga-renewable.es.tl/>) is another free tool from the University of Zaragoza in Spain which employs genetic algorithms to find near-optimum solutions in a reasonable amount of time. Also, RETScreen (<http://www.nrcan.gc.ca/energy/software-tools/7465>) is an Excel-based software package, developed by the Government of Canada, which relies on statistical models rather than detailed time-series simulations; thus, it can be used as a first step in planning a renewable energy project.

IV. PERFORMANCE OF ENERGY HARVESTING MULTI-HOP BACKHAULS

Energy harvesting has received much attention in the wireless communication literature, with a large body of work focusing on techniques that allow communication networks to operate optimally with limited energy. In this context, mathematical models capturing the interactions between the information and energy planes have been proposed based on queueing theory [35], [36], risk theory [37] and diffusion processes [38]. The models enable the study of networks and operational conditions that can balance the energy needs for sensing, communications and computing, with the availability of renewable and intermittent sources of energy, so as to achieve energy neutrality [39]. While most of these studies focus on the fundamental analysis and optimisation methods that can be used in energy harvesting wireless and wired communications, they do not specifically address mobile networks, nor do they propose architectures or overall system designs.

The abstraction of an "energy packet network" (EPN) [40], [41], whereby the amount of energy needed to transmit a single data packet is represented as a discrete quantity, provides a way forward. In recent work, techniques have been developed in [42] for optimising the flow of a mix of renewable and fuel generated energy sources to simultaneously address multiple real-time needs of consumption by ICT systems, with utility functions that can be used to prioritise these needs. As the

underlying queueing model assumes steady-state conditions, these methods must be adapted to account for temporal variability in energy and load profiles.

In this section, we will show how this approach can be used to analyse the performance of the multi-hop backbone of a mobile network. Indeed, although there is much research on the radio link between mobile devices and BSs, the main power consumption occurs in the BSs and in the multi-hop and packet based network that connects BSs. We assume that the backbone network operates in packet mode so that all the calls flow in the form of data packets (DPs). Although a voice call usually requires a bilateral flow of packets, modern mobile phone systems also carry web accesses and downloads, and download traffic may actually dominate the backbone. Thus we will not specifically include the bilateral nature of the flow. Also, we will assume that the critical resource in this system is energy, rather than bandwidth, because we focus on a system that is primarily operating with harvested energy.

Thus we will consider a set of nodes, denote them n_1, \dots, n_N , where the first and N -th nodes may be base stations or servers, while the intermediate nodes are routers or packet switches, and each of them operates by harvesting energy. We will consider a mobile telephone connection or "user", which transmits a flow of DPs along the full path n_1 to n_N that need to traverse each of the nodes, and we assume that if a DP cannot be forwarded (or transmitted in the case of wireless relays) by node i to node $i+1$, $1 \leq i \leq N$, then it is lost and will have to be retransmitted with some probability p . A packet is also lost if node n_N is unable to forward or retransmit the packet to the end user. In the sequel we simplify matters by assuming that the only reason for a packet to be lost on the path is that at least one of the nodes has run out of energy. The probability p recognises the fact that only a fraction p of DPs belong to flows (such as IP connections) where a lost packet has to be retransmitted as with IP flows that relate to data content.

We will assume that each of the nodes operates with energy received at node i is either being harvested at rate γ_i^H , or received from the grid at rate γ_i^G , or both, so that the total energy supply rates at the nodes are $\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_N$, where $\gamma_i = \gamma_i^H + \gamma_i^G$, respectively. Note that in the types of systems we are studying, not only is γ_i^H the average value of an intermittent, i.e. random, process, but so is γ_i^G because the power from the electricity grid varies with time due to overloads, instability, and unreliable energy sources and unreliable power lines and transformers. These rates are given in Energy Packets (EP) per second, where an EP is a unit that corresponds to the energy consumed by the corresponding node to process and forward one data packet. By this we mean that an energy packet at node i is not necessarily the amount of energy in an energy packet at node j for $i \neq j$. However, since we can identify the node i , then knowing its energy consumption characteristics, we can identify the specific value (in Joules) of one energy packet at that node. Thus γ_i represents the average inflow of power (EPs/sec) to node i normalised to that node's energy consumption for one data packet that is processed and forwarded at the node.

The EPs received by any node are first stored in a battery

or “energy store (ES)”. For simplicity, we assume that this battery has unlimited capacity, although this assumption can be relaxed and we can still carry out the type of analysis described below. We also suppose that the battery at n_i leaks at rate δ_i , so that one EP is lost at the battery at i in an exponentially distributed time of average value δ_i^{-1} ; again we assume that this quantity is given at node i in local units of EPs/sec.

In addition to the end-to-end user connection which is assumed to input fresh user traffic at a rate of λ DPs/sec, each node n_i locally receives another traffic flow of Λ_i DPs/sec. The arrival processes for both DPs are assumed to be independent Poisson processes. Furthermore all DP service times are independent and exponentially distributed. Since we focus on the effect of the possible lack of energy at the nodes, we ignore the packet losses due to buffer overflow or errors.

A. System without Data Storage at the Nodes

We first consider an ideal system where each node uses energy very efficiently, and does not consume energy at all when there are no packets at a node. Thus we assume also that the nodes are so efficient that they *only* use energy when they process, forward (or transmit) a packet. We also assume that the nodes are fast enough, and the traffic rates small enough in comparison, so that DPs do not queue at the nodes. In this case, the loss probability L_i at node i is the probability that the energy at that node is depleted [41], or equivalently that its battery is empty:

$$L_i = 1 - \frac{\gamma_i}{\delta_i + \Lambda_i + \lambda_i}, \quad (1)$$

where λ_i is the user traffic entering node $2 \leq i \leq N$ on the path:

$$\lambda_i = (1 - L_{i-1})\lambda_{i-1} = \lambda_1 \prod_{j=1}^{i-1} (1 - L_j). \quad (2)$$

Note that:

$$\frac{\gamma_i}{\delta_i + \Lambda_i + \lambda_i}, \quad (3)$$

is the probability that the node’s battery does contain at least one EP, and this formula does *not* require that EPs arrive to the node’s battery according to a Poisson process, nor that the EP inter-leakage and depletion times are exponentially distributed. Indeed, the EP depletion process can be represented as a mix of service times (leakage) and negative customers (energy consumption) and such systems have been studied [43] with general arrival and service times.

The total DP loss probability L on the path is then:

$$L = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^N (1 - L_i). \quad (4)$$

Now if λ is a given value of the traffic rate of DPs that the user forwards on the path, then the effective user flow rate entering at node n_1 includes this traffic plus the traffic from all the DPs that need to be forwarded, namely:

$$\lambda_1 = \lambda + p.L.\lambda_1 = \frac{\lambda}{1 - p.L}, \quad (5)$$

where p and λ are given, while L is calculated from (4).

B. Nodes with Packet Storage

In the previous section, batteries are represented by queues that store EPs, while the assumption is made that the system is so fast and the traffic sufficiently small that DP queues need not be represented. Now, again using the EPN formalism [40], we extend the approach to the case where each node n_i on the path from n_1 to n_N has a queue of unlimited length which stores DPs and services them in first-in-first-out (FIFO) order. Furthermore, in the present case we assume that the node uses the same amount of energy even when it has no DPs to forward, i.e. when its DP queue is empty. These assumptions are realistic when a node has to remain awake constantly to manage various functions it needs to accomplish, in addition to forwarding packets.

We will assume that the packet forwarding and transmission time at node n_i is exponentially distributed with parameter μ_i , and during that time an EP is consumed at node i whether it is idle or not. Finite capacity queues can also be studied, but with current technologies buffer capacities are large enough so that we need not consider this limitation in the first instance. Thus the DPs that belong to the connection (user) that runs along this path will move packets at rate λ_1 into the first node’s queue and at rate λ_i into the DP queue at n_i , though in this case these values are not the same as in (4) because the loss probabilities have changed. Although some semiconductor memories may lose the stored data when the power supply is interrupted, one can expect that in this case the memory technology that is used is able to save the data even when there is an interruption in the power supply, so that only those packets which are at the head of the queue and are being transmitted may be lost.

Now using the approach in [41], on we compute the probability π_i that the power supply is *not* interrupted due to lack of energy at node n_i :

$$\pi_i = \frac{\gamma_i}{\delta_i + \mu_i}, \quad (6)$$

since we have assumed that the nodes consume energy independently of the packet forwarding rate. We wish to point out that the formula for π_i does *not* depend on assuming that the arrival process of EPs is Poisson, and that the EP depletion intervals for leakage and energy are exponentially distributed. Indeed, the formula is broadly valid for general EP inter-arrival and removal processes.

The probability ρ_i that the DP queue n_i is non-empty is:

$$\rho_i = \frac{\lambda_i + \Lambda_i}{\pi_i \cdot \mu_i}, \quad (7)$$

since energy replenishment and depletion is assumed to be independent of the workload at the node when the node is kept on constantly, whether it is processing DPs or not, as long as energy is available. In the sequel we consider two cases: a system equipped with a memory for DPs which can store packets (and not lose them) even when its energy supply is depleted, and one which loses all stored packets when it runs out of energy.

C. DPs Stored in a Node are not Lost due to lack of Energy

In this favorable case, when a node has run out of energy some DPs will be lost, namely those DPs that are arriving into the node, plus the DPs being forwarded from the nodes when they run out of energy. All other stored DPs will remain in memory, and will be forwarded later when the node's battery again contains energy. Thus for any node i we define λ_i^I as the total *user traffic flowing in the N -node path that enters the node*. λ_i^O is the total user traffic flowing in the path that leaves node i . Then: for we will have:

$$\lambda_1^I = \lambda_e \pi_1, \text{ and } \lambda_i^I = \lambda_{i-1}^O \pi_i, \quad 2 \leq i \leq N, \quad (8)$$

where λ_e is the total user traffic (including packet retransmissions due to losses) that enters the N -node path, and whenever the node has energy then it will be able to input and store an incoming DP, but the incoming DP will be lost if the node runs out of energy. Also:

$$\lambda_i^O = \frac{\lambda_i^I}{\lambda_i^I + \Lambda_i} \mu_i \rho_i \pi_i, \quad (9)$$

because the outgoing DP is a user DP on the N -node path with probability $\frac{\lambda_i^I}{\lambda_i^I + \Lambda_i}$. There will be an outgoing DP at rate μ_i when there are DPs stored in the node, which occurs with probability ρ_i . Since in this case we have:

$$\rho_i = \frac{\lambda_i^I + \Lambda_i}{\mu_i \pi_i}, \quad (10)$$

we remain with:

$$\lambda_i^O = \lambda_i^I, \text{ and } \lambda_N^O = \lambda_e \prod_{i=1}^N \pi_i. \quad (11)$$

Since all of the lost packets have to be retransmitted, for an arrival rate λ of fresh user DPs that arrive to the first node, we will have a total effective arrival rate of packets:

$$\lambda_e = \frac{\lambda}{1 - p \cdot [1 - \prod_{i=1}^N \frac{\gamma_i}{\delta_i + \mu_i}]}, \quad (12)$$

and

$$\lambda_i^I = \lambda_e \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{i-1} \frac{\gamma_j}{\delta_j + \mu_j}. \quad (13)$$

V. WHEN STORED DPs ARE LOST FOR LACK OF ENERGY

Contrary to Section IV-C, in this section we assume that if a node runs out of energy, all the packets stored at the node will be lost. This is a worst case, and it also needs to be considered. As in Section IV-C, we assume that each node is being constantly powered and that its energy consumption is independent of its workload, so that the probability π_i that a node's battery is *not* depleted is given by (6).

The analysis we develop is based upon upon exact analytical results concerning G-Networks with "batch removal" (sometimes also called "catastrophes") [44], [45], for the cascade network of queues that models the N nodes along the path from source to destination. Each node $i \geq 2$ receives DPs at rate λ_i^C from its predecessor node upstream. It also receives DPs in a Poisson process at rate Λ_i directly from other sources.

The first node receives a total end user traffic of λ_E which includes the external arrivals from the user which is assumed to be a Poisson flow of rate λ .

The first node on the path receives the end user's DPs in a Poisson process of rate λ from outside the network, and when the i -th node's battery is non-empty with probability π_i computed from (6), it forwards user packets at rate μ_i to its successor, and the "cross" traffic entering the node at rate Λ_i just leaves the node after a service time. On the other hand, if at the end of a DP service time the node's battery is depleted, which occurs with probability $D_i = 1 - \pi_i$, then all the DPs at node i are lost.

Using the analysis for an arbitrarily interconnected network of this kind in [44], for $2 \leq i \leq N$ we obtain the probability q_i that node i is busy serving DPs, as the non-linear expression:

$$q_i = \frac{\Lambda_i + \lambda_i^C}{\mu_i \cdot \pi_i + \mu_i \cdot D_i \frac{q_i}{1 - q_i}}, \quad (14)$$

where:

$$\lambda_i^C = \frac{\lambda_{i-1}^C}{\lambda_{i-1}^C + \Lambda_i} q_{i-1} \cdot \mu_{i-1} \pi_{i-1}. \quad (15)$$

For the first node on the path we have:

$$q_1 = \frac{\Lambda_1 + \lambda_E}{\mu_1 \cdot \pi_1 + \mu_1 \cdot D_1 \frac{q_1}{1 - q_1}}. \quad (16)$$

Thus we can compute the loss probability L_1^C of end-user DPs going through node 1 as:

$$1 - L_1^C = \frac{q_1 \mu_1 \pi_1}{\lambda_E} \frac{\lambda_E}{\Lambda_1 + \lambda_E} = [1 + \frac{q_1(1 - \pi_1)}{\pi_1(1 - q_1)}]^{-1}, \quad (17)$$

and for the loss L_i^C through node $2 \leq i \leq N$, using (14) we will have:

$$1 - L_i^C = \frac{q_i \mu_i \pi_i}{\lambda_i^C} \frac{\lambda_i^C}{\Lambda_i + \lambda_i^C} = [1 + \frac{q_i(1 - \pi_i)}{\pi_i(1 - q_i)}]^{-1}. \quad (18)$$

The effective rate at which user packets enter the path (including packet retransmissions) is then:

$$\lambda_E = \lambda + p \lambda_E [1 - \prod_{i=1}^N (1 - L_i^C)], \quad (19)$$

or obviously:

$$\lambda_E = \frac{\lambda}{1 - p [1 - \prod_{i=1}^N (1 - L_i^C)]}. \quad (20)$$

A. Numerical Examples

In Figure 1 we illustrate the analytical results with numerical examples that compare all three cases considered in Sections IV and V. We plot the curves for three values of the total number of nodes N on the multi-hop path (1, 5, and 10) and assume that all the $\gamma_i = 0.9$, $\delta_i = 0.1$, $\Lambda_i = 0.9$ are identical with a user traffic rate of $\lambda = 0.1$ DP/sec and $\mu = 1$ DP/sec. The x -axis represents the proportion p of lost DPs that need to be retransmitted, ranging from 0.1 to 1. The y -axis is the total average number of DP retransmissions per forwarded user packet.

Fig. 1. Average number of transmissions per DP versus the fraction p of DPs that must be retransmitted if lost. The length of the path traversed by user traffic is varied with $N = 1, 5, 10$ hops. Other parameters are $\lambda = 0.1$ DP/sec, $\Lambda = 0.9$ DP/sec, $\gamma = 0.9$ EP/sec, $\delta = 0.1$ EP/sec, and the service rate of the DPs is $\mu = 0.9$ DP/s.

In Figure 2 we plot the total loss probability L and the average number of transmissions per DP against p and against λ . When packets are not stored at intermediate nodes, we see that the loss probability is more sensitive to λ than p , both of which contribute to congestion and energy depletion; but the effect of p is more pronounced on the number of retransmissions. On the other hand, both parameters have no effect on the loss probability when the node consumes the same amount of EPs when it is idle and when it is not idle. However, if all packets stored at a node are lost when the node runs out of energy, then the multi-hop path experiences much higher packet loss which does not vary significantly with λ or p , while the number of retransmissions grow very fast with p .

Figure 3 compares the two cases with DPs storage, with regard to the total average packet delay for user packets. The total end-to-end delay includes the retransmissions due to packet loss, and includes all the possible times a packet spends in transit before it is successfully forwarded by each of the N nodes. We set $N = 3$ and the rate of cross traffic at each node $\Lambda = 0.5$ DP/sec which does not overflow the DP queues. We vary λ between 0.1 and 0.2 and plot the results for three values of p to represent the nature of the traffic mix ranging from data oriented user traffic with $p = 0.9$, to traffic such as voice with $p = 0.1$ and balanced traffic with $p = 0.5$. The results show that for small values of λ , the total average delay is significantly lower when DPs are not lost for lack of energy. However this is only observed for small values of λ . When λ increases beyond certain levels, the end-to-end delays are significantly increased by the presence of the stored packets that are forwarded at each node before the packets that arrive from the end-to-end traffic encounters. Thus in a certain sense, the massive packet losses at the nodes that are unable to store packets when they run out of energy, have an interesting “randomising or round-robin effect” which result in an increase of the priority of the end-to-end packets which do not have to wait for the previously stored packets to be

served in first-in-first-out order.

VI. OPTIMISATION FRAMEWORKS

Each of a mobile network components has a purchase or leasing cost and an operating cost or barriers that are related to the availability of technical expertise. The system as a whole can generate income via the mobile users (typically via the purchase of communication time, or even device recharging time), and government subsidies (for instance for public services that are supported by the mobile network). Thus, an area of active research focuses on deriving a methodology to select an optimal mix and capacity of equipment (BSs and their technologies, photovoltaic sources, diesel generators, batteries, vehicles and recharging stations) so as to minimise CAPEX and OPEX, while meeting specified levels of coverage at specified hours of day and night.

The feasibility of a renewable powered LTE BS under typical *urban* traffic conditions is investigated in [46]. Results of dimensioning PV panels and battery size for a *macro* BS indicate that the size of the renewable energy system is impractical for locations with large solar variability, but can be reduced to an acceptable level with the use of BS sleep modes. A similar dimensioning problem under a power outage constraint is considered in [9], where battery lifetime and outage probability are estimated using Markov models and simulations. These and other studies [9], [16], [46] confirm our earlier observation that it is preferable to have more small cells with small renewable energy systems than a few larger cells.

The effect of putting BSs to sleep is evaluated in [47] by formulating a complex optimisation problem that targets reducing CAPEX for PV panels and batteries under QoS constraints in terms of minimum throughput, blocking probability and power outage. A heuristic for solving the optimisation problem which also includes user assignment to BSs and power control is developed [47] and validated using simulation results with data from a real operator. A limitation of this formulation however is that it relies on a linear model for various expenditures, the coefficients of which are all system and individual implementation-dependent, making it difficult to draw conclusions in terms of optimal operating conditions.

The above methods attempt to fulfil QoS demands of mobile users with minimum CAPEX assuming a fixed network topology of one or more BSs. They do not address the node placement aspect of the network planning phase, which is considered in [48], [49] in the context of green WLAN. The resulting optimisation problem – finding the minimum number of renewable-operated APs that must be deployed to satisfy throughput and battery depletion probability requirements – is a mixed integer nonlinear program which is known to be NP-hard. Thus, the authors [48] propose a heuristic algorithm that incorporates power control and rate adaptation at APs, which is shown to achieve good performance. In many situations, however, the locations of the APs are determined based on connectivity requirements and non-technical reasons, but other aspects such as tower heights, transmit powers and topology may still be optimised [22]. For energy-efficient operation of

Fig. 2. The end-to-end loss probability (top) and average number of transmissions per DP (bottom) against the DP rate λ and the fraction p of DPs that must be retransmitted if lost. The number of hops in the path traversed by the user traffic is fixed at $N = 3$, while the other parameters are as in Figure 1.

Fig. 3. Total average packet delay (including delays that accrue due to retransmissions of lost packets) versus the arrival rate λ for $p = 0.1, 0.5$, and 0.9 . The number of nodes on the multi-hop path is $N = 3$ and each node receives additional traffic with rate $\Lambda = 0.5$ DP/sec. The other parameters are as in Figure 1.

off-grid networks, a joint power assignment and cell association policy is developed in [16] based on the threshold-bisection method. Numerical results show that the proposed suboptimal solution is able to balance the energy usage at different BSs, while taking into account future availability of energy at each BS.

A. Energy-Aware Scheduling

Energy efficient packet scheduling is also an important research area since the early 2000s. Lazy scheduling [50] transmits packets at the minimum rate and power necessary to satisfy certain requirements such as delay, deadline or energy budget. Routing to minimize energy consumption is discussed in [51]. Recently, energy harvesting constraints have

been incorporated into the scheduling problem [52]–[54], and optimal policies have been developed for offline settings [55]–[61] where non-causal knowledge of energy and data arrival profiles is available, and for online but infinite horizon versions of the problem [57], [60]–[67] where optimisation is carried out over a long time scale. A drawback of offline frameworks is that the resulting policies do not provide much insight for designing efficient algorithms that can be used in practice. On the other hand, most online formulations assume a priori knowledge of the statistical characteristics of the data and energy profiles, i.e. they assume the future evolution of the system is governed by stochastic models whose parameters are known or can be estimated reliably. In some practical scenarios, however, energy intake can vary strongly over time as do the wireless channel conditions and the traffic that needs

to be transmitted or carried through the network. In such cases, infinite-horizon policies have been shown to perform poorly even over fairly long time periods [56].

Thus, finite-horizon online optimisation has been explored under mild restrictions [56] and no restrictions [68] regarding the statistical information available at the transmitter. Also, learning methods based on forecasting [69], [70], adaptive control theory [71] and reinforcement learning [72], [73] have been employed to adapt in real-time the transmission strategy or duty-cycle according to learned characteristics of the environment.

VII. CONCLUDING REMARKS

We have surveyed the main challenges, opportunities and incentives associated with deploying energy harvesting wireless services in rural areas in Africa and other parts of the developing world where power from the grid may be unreliable or too costly. We outlined the main requirements and discussed the related enabling technologies. This paper also introduced a novel queueing theory based approach to analyse the packet loss probabilities and related quality of service of multi-hop backhaul networks in the presence of intermittent and unreliable node power supplies. We expect that future work can build on these premises to develop design methodologies for mobile networks when energy sources are intermittent or unreliable.

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